

LESSONS LEARNED IN 2020

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The year 2020 was unique to this Journal for several reasons, good and bad. We have received a few hundred manuscripts during this year and tried to select the best ones for publication.

After almost 20 years of adopting one publishing model, it is certainly time to do a good PDCA cycle. Some of the challenges that we are improving for 2021 are related to the Journal pre-prints, cover letter, and other minor issues.

- Regarding the Journal pre-prints, for almost 17 years, we provided pre-prints that matched very close with the final file. We noticed this year that it is better to make the pre-prints as a limited view of the final version instead of as closer as possible to the final approved version. Therefore, the authors who publish with us for many years will notice a difference in the preview files format already in the end of 2020. As the Journal does not provide ahead of print (AOP) solutions, it will avoid misunderstandings by the authors.
- Review time. As the Journal grows in new countries, the average time of review of 60 days will need to change. For some countries, the average time for the evaluation will be extended to up to 180 days as the number of manuscripts is significant, and the communication with the authors is more difficult due to linguistic challenges.
- The cover letter file was also updated and improved. The new file makes it simpler for the authors to inform if they are eligible for any available discount opportunities. Pages 2 to 6 illustrate the new version of the cover letter.
- Predicted calendar for 2021 will be March, July, and November. Plan the publication of the manuscript with sufficient review time.

On behalf of all the journal team, we are grateful to all the authors and institutions that have worked with us over the last 17 years. We hope to provide a good quality service for the next 17 years.

COVER LETTER FOR SUBMISSION OF MANUSCRIPT

Date:

Editor-in-Chief

Tchê Química Journal

359 Anita Garibaldi Street.

Mont' Serrat, Zip Code: 90450-001

Porto Alegre/RS - Brazil

Subject: **SUBMISSION OF A MANUSCRIPT FOR EVALUATION**

Title:

Keywords:

Authors:

Corresponding author details:

Full Name:

Full correspondence address (including):

Name of the institution:

Department Name:

Full Address:

Town/city:

State/Province:

Country:

Phone:

E-mail:

Zip Code:

Dear Editor

I, the corresponding author of the manuscript, am enclosing herewith a paper for publication in **TCHÊ QUÍMICA JOURNAL** for possible evaluation.

With the submission of this manuscript, I would like to undertake that:

- All authors of this research paper have directly participated in the planning, execution, or analysis of this study;
- All authors of this paper have read and approved the final version submitted;
- The contents of this manuscript have not been copyrighted or published previously;
- The contents of this manuscript are not now under consideration for publication elsewhere;

- The contents of this manuscript will not be copyrighted, submitted, or published elsewhere, while acceptance by the Journal is under consideration;
- There are no directly related manuscripts or abstracts, published or unpublished, by any authors of this paper;
- My Institute's representative is fully aware of this submission.
- **ATTENTION: ETHICS COMMITTEE APPROVAL ON RESEARCH WITH HUMAN OR ANIMAL PARTICIPANTS**

Research on human participants, which includes identifiable human material or identifiable data, requires ethical protection. According to the *Declaration of Helsinki* issued by the World Medical Association, research on human participants should be clearly formulated in experimental protocols, and these should be submitted to independent ethical review boards (ethics committees and institutional review boards) for approval. Additionally, every potential participant should be informed about the "aims, methods, sources of funding, any possible conflicts of interest, institutional affiliations of the researcher, the anticipated benefits and potential risks of the study and the discomfort it may entail" and should give consent to participate.

Source: S Schroter, R Plowman, A Hutchings, A Gonzalez; Reporting ethics committee approval and patient consent by study design in five general medical journals. *J Med Ethics* 2006; 32:718–723. DOI: 10.1136/jme.2005.015115.

- **Authors are required to describe in their manuscripts ethics committee approval and participants consent by study design from participants when research involves human participants.**

Ethics approval must be sought for research involving human participants.

A 'participant' is someone who:

- Actively provides research data. For example:
 - ✓ Completes surveys
 - ✓ Participates in interviews, discussions or observations
 - ✓ Undergoes psychological, physiological or medical treatment or testing
 - ✓ tests software
 - ✓ Grants access to personal collections of records, photographs, etc.
 - ✓ Is the person from whom tissue has been collected (including blood, urine, saliva, hair)
 - ✓ Is identified in a record, e.g., employment record, medical record, education record, membership list, electoral roll or
 - ✓ Is identified or de-identified in data banks or unpublished human research data, e.g., analysis of existing unpublished data collected by another researcher or collected for a different research project.

Source: <https://www.newcastle.edu.au/research-and-innovation/resources/human-ethics/what-needs-ethics-approval>, accessed on November 23rd, 2019

- **Authors are required to describe in their manuscripts the Animal Ethics Committee approval when the study is carried out using animals.**

Animal Ethics Committees (AECs) provide avenues for public participation in the regulation of animal research. AECs are responsible for approving and monitoring research within Accredited Animal Research Establishments, including carrying out inspections of animals and facilities.

No animal research may be carried out without AEC approval. AECs must consider and evaluate applications to conduct research on the basis of the researchers' responses to a comprehensive set of questions, including their justification for the research, its likely impact on the animals, and procedures for preventing or alleviating pain and distress.

On behalf of the establishment, AECs have the power to stop inappropriate research and to discipline researchers by withdrawing their research approvals. They can require that adequate care, including emergency care, is provided for animals. They also provide guidance and support to researchers on matters relevant to animal welfare, through means such as the preparation of guidelines and dissemination of relevant scientific literature. AECs are responsible for advising establishments on the changes to physical facilities that should be made to provide for the needs of the animals used.

Source: <https://www.animaletics.org.au/animal-ethics-committees>, accessed on November 23rd, 2019

Does your research is based on human or animal participants?

(Select one option with a cross in the appropriate box)

YES:	NO:
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If YES, please provide the Animal Ethics Committee Approval Number or Ethics Committee Approval and patient consent by study design

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Will you require a letter of acceptance?*

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YES:	NO:
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* The acceptance letter is an **optional service** of the Journal. If the authors need a document to prove that their article has been peer-reviewed and accepted for publication, they may request, upon payment of an additional fee of USD 40, an acceptance letter for publication of the article.

NOTE 1: THE LETTER OF ACCEPTANCE may be issued **if, and only if**, the article has undergone a complete peer-review and is considered ACCEPTED for publication. Letters will NOT be issued for newly sent articles that have not yet been appropriately evaluated and peer-reviewed.

NOTE 2: The Journal does not agree with the trade-in documents that can attest to the publication of articles that have not gone through the due process of peer-review and are legitimately considered approved for publication in the subsequent edition.

NOTE 3: THE LETTER OF ACCEPTANCE may be revoked at any time if, concerns about the manuscript emerge.

Will you require formatting services?

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This is an optional service. Not free of cost.

The submitted manuscript is a **(Select one option with a cross in the appropriate box)**

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Book review	
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Clinical Trial	
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Any other (specify the type of manuscript)	

Any other (specify the type of manuscript).....

.....

For the Editors, I would like to disclose the following information about the project: **(If any, please write here)**

The research project was conducted under the supervision of:

(Provide the name of the Supervisor with his/her complete information)

The research project was my: **(Select one option with a cross in the appropriate box)**

Undergraduate project	
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I am aware that the journal does not provide ahead of print publication. I will not share any type of pre-print prior to the printing of the journal.

I am aware that the journal may review my manuscript at anytime prior to the publication, and postpone or exclude it from publication if concerns are raised regarding the authorship, authenticity, or other undesirable issues that may occur.

Are you eligible for discounts and Free publication opportunities? If so, please select the appropriate check box:

- a) 50% discount for authors who support other journals from the team (Southern Brazilian Journal of Chemistry), with 1 manuscript approved for publication;
- b) 100% discount for authors who support other journals from the team (Southern Brazilian Journal of Chemistry), with 2 manuscripts approved for publication;
- c) Volume discount if you are an author of the journal, that has published with us 4 manuscripts (paid your full corresponded price), your fifth manuscript will be free of charge. Later the counting cycle restart.
- d) Young scientists that are publishing the first manuscript of their career. Requirements: Copy of the curriculum without publications; maximum of 2 authors; one manuscript previously accepted in the Southern Brazilian Journal of Chemistry (the manuscript may be from the author or from colleagues, provided that the extra purpose of the collaboration is notified at the time of submission), or two manuscripts previously accepted Journal of Law, Public Policies, and Human Sciences (manuscripts may be from the author or from colleagues, provided that the extra purpose of the collaboration is notified at the time of submission). (Last revision of the rule: 10/15/2020)
- e) All personal related to the production of the journals, from Brazil and abroad;
- f) Longtime collaborators. The authors who published four (4) articles during the first decade of the journal, will be rewarded with one (1) free publication.
- g) Paper considered by the Editors of high quality, priority, and relevance for the development of the society shall pay no fees. Note that this condition is a small recognition prize, not something that you may request. Thank you for your comprehension.
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